

Job Satisfaction Towards Attitudes and Career Motivation of the Physical Education Instructors in Selected Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro

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Abstract

This study investigated the extent of the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation among Physical Education (PE) teachers in the selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro, and whether job satisfaction acts a moderating factor to attitude toward physical activity and career motivation. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected from the nine (9) PE instructors who were chosen using total enumeration from the selected higher education institutions, and were analyzed through linear regression and ANOVA techniques. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire which was validated and tested for reliability. The findings revealed that attitude toward physical activity significantly predicts career motivation. Teachers who held more

favorable views toward physical activity tended to exhibit higher levels of motivation in their teaching careers. However, further analysis showed that job satisfaction did not significantly moderate either the teachers' attitudes or their career motivation. Regardless of satisfaction levels, the respondents maintained consistent motivation and attitudes. These results emphasize the value of fostering positive attitudes toward physical activity as a means to sustain and enhance professional motivation. For administrators and educational institutions, the findings suggest that teacher development programs focused on promoting wellness and reinforcing professional commitment may yield more impact than those focused solely on improving job satisfaction.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, attitude in physical activities, career motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Perceived Gap

While much research exists on student motivation, less is known about the attitudes of PE instructors themselves toward physical activity and how these attitudes shape their motivation for choosing teaching as a career. This gap is significant for understanding how PE programs are taught and perceived at the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro. Although research has addressed the attitudes

of PE instructors toward physical activity and their career motivation, the role of job satisfaction as a moderating factor in this relationship is underexplored. Understanding this moderating effect could provide information on why some instructors are more motivated than others.

Adding job satisfaction as a moderating variable will help clarify the PE instructors' attitudes toward physical activity and their motivation to teach. Identifying how job satisfaction influences this relationship could lead to possible improvements in job conditions and teaching quality at the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

Background of the Study

Job satisfaction plays a vital role in shaping the professional lives of educators, influencing their performance, commitment, and motivation to continue in their chosen careers (Salas-Vallina et al., 2020). For Physical Education (PE) instructors, both their attitudes toward physical activity and their career motivation are critical to their effectiveness in promoting active lifestyles among students (Trigueros et al., 2019). Positive attitudes toward physical activity not only foster the physical health of the educators but also enhance their enthusiasm in teaching, which can subsequently improve student outcomes in physical education (Cale, 2023).

However, despite the acknowledged importance of attitudes and career motivation in education, research on the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between these factors among PE instructors is limited. While studies suggest that instructors with a strong positive attitude toward physical activity tend to be more motivated to teach (Kara, & Ada, 2021), the extent to which job satisfaction influences this relationship has yet to be fully explored (Van den Berghe et al., 2020). It is possible that PE instructors who are satisfied with their jobs may demonstrate higher levels of motivation, regardless of their attitudes toward physical activity, while those with lower job satisfaction might struggle to maintain motivation even if they have a positive attitude toward the subject.

At the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro, physical education instructors are faced with a variety of challenges, including limited resources, large class sizes, and the growing emphasis on academic rather than physical achievements (Duda et al., 2019). These challenges could potentially impact their job satisfaction and, consequently, their career motivation. Understanding how job satisfaction moderates the relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation is therefore essential in identifying ways to support and sustain the professional growth of PE instructors in such environments.

The need for this study is further explained by the fact that physical education plays a crucial role in developing students' lifelong habits of physical activity and health. If PE instructors are not sufficiently motivated, the quality of education and the promotion of physical activity in students may suffer (Ntoumanis et al., 2020). Thus, this study aimed to examine the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation of PE instructors among the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro. Investigating this relationship seeks to provide insights into the factors that influence PE instructors' motivation, which could inform policies and strategies for improving job satisfaction and career motivation in the field of physical education.

Review of Related Literature

This section presents several related literature and studies about attitudes toward physical activity, job satisfaction, and career motivation for teaching physical education of the physical education teachers that could better help understand the said variables of this study.

Attitudes Towards Physical Activities of Physical Education Teachers

Gumanoy et al. (2022) investigated the attitudes and acceptability of physical education among Madrasah teachers in five Madaris schools in Marawi City, Lanao del Sur, Philippines. This descriptive study involved 290 Madrasah teachers (190 females, 100 males), using total enumeration. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale, which addressed demographic information, attitudes toward physical activity, and the acceptability of integrating physical education into the Madrasah curriculum. The findings showed that most respondents were female (65.52%), aged 31–40 years (37.94%), with the majority holding a *Koliah* (college-level) education (68.97%) or a bachelor's degree in Western education (43.44%). Most teachers had 6–10 years of service (38.27%) and were teaching at the elementary level (34.48%). The study revealed a positive attitude toward physical activity and a high level of acceptance of physical education within the curriculum. The researchers emphasized the need to design activity programs tailored to the needs and interests of Madrasah teachers and students. They recommended involving CSPEAR faculty, in collaboration with school administrators and directors of Arabic schools in Marawi City, to promote the value of physical education and encourage greater participation in physical activities.

Marques et al. (2022) conducted a study to explore how Portuguese physical education teachers perceive the role of fitness tests in developing physical fitness in schools. The study involved 764 middle and high school teachers in Portugal, with data collected using the Physical Education Teacher Attitudes Toward Fitness Tests Scale (PETAFTS). The means and confidence intervals for each attitude subdomain and overall attitudes were calculated, and a one-way ANOVA was applied to examine group differences across three attitude subdomains based on various variables. On a 7-point Likert scale, teachers' overall attitude toward fitness tests was slightly positive (5.52, 95% CI: 5.47, 5.58). The findings indicated that female teachers viewed fitness tests as more useful, whereas male teachers significantly enjoyed implementing them. Additionally, younger teachers reported greater enjoyment in administering fitness tests compared to their older counterparts. The study concluded that future research should focus on designing intervention strategies that consider both gender and age to enhance the promotion of physical fitness through fitness tests in schools.

Furthermore, Kiran's (2017) study explores teachers' perspectives on participating in physical activities and the factors motivating them to pursue a career in teaching physical education. Data was collected using two questionnaires, involving 98 participants. This research revealed that the participants held a positive view of physical activity. Additionally, the study identified both internal and external motivations for choosing a career in physical education. A correlation was observed between the participants' attitudes toward physical exercise and their reasons for entering the physical education profession.

Relacion (2023) examined the connection between burnout and attitudes towards physical activity among public junior high school teachers as a foundation for an intervention plan. This quantitative research employed a descriptive-correlation design and utilized adapted questionnaires for data collection. The

statistical methods used to analyze the data included mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, and linear regression. The results showed that the burnout level among public junior high teachers was low, while their attitudes towards physical activity were rated high. Additionally, a significant relationship was found between burnout and attitudes towards physical activity. Among the three burnout domains, only depersonalization significantly influenced the teachers' attitudes towards physical activity. Based on these findings, an intervention plan for teachers was developed.

Job Satisfaction of the Physical Education Teachers

Employment holds a significant role in human life, as it provides individuals with the means to fulfil their social, financial, and psychological needs. Through their jobs, people contribute to economic productivity, earn income, and support themselves and their families. Furthermore, employment serves social purposes by defining social status, which fosters a sense of contributing to society, facilitates interactions, and builds new relationships. It also offers psychological benefits, such as the pride of having a job, the joy of productivity, the excitement of starting new tasks, the satisfaction of success, and the fulfilment of engaging in meaningful work (Çakır, 2001, as cited by Yuceloglu Keskin & Bayram, 2020).

Gazali et al. (2024) revealed that administrative support, work-life balance, and economic factors significantly affect the job satisfaction of physical education teachers. Additionally, aspects such as financial incentives, working conditions, and resource availability also contribute to their overall satisfaction. The study highlights the importance of understanding the various factors that influence job satisfaction among physical education instructors to inform the development of policies and practices that enhance teacher well-being and performance on both local and global scales.

Meanwhile, Hao et al. (2018) examined the job satisfaction levels of 300 physical education (PE) teachers from 20 primary and secondary schools in Shandong Province. The study revealed that, overall, PE teachers experienced a moderate level of job satisfaction. They reported the highest satisfaction in working conditions and interpersonal relationships, while satisfaction with the school system, leadership support, and work environment was relatively lower. Male PE teachers demonstrated higher job satisfaction than their female counterparts, although no significant differences were found beyond gender. Additionally, young PE teachers with 0–2 years of experience reported greater satisfaction with leadership support compared to teachers with more years of experience. In terms of school systems, salary, and welfare, senior teachers expressed significantly higher satisfaction than intermediate and junior teachers.

Career Motivation for Teaching Physical Education of the Physical Education Teachers

Zhang (2021) offered a theoretical perspective which suggests that physical education teacher motivation is shaped by the context, closely linked to job demands and resources. The study also presents a reconceptualized theoretical framework for future research, drawing on extrinsic motivation and the job demand–job resource model. A literature review of theory-driven, data-based studies on physical education teacher motivation highlighted the need to refine and unify theoretical perspectives to strengthen future research. The review further indicates that to better understand physical education teacher motivation, it is essential to examine the psychological and behavioral processes involved, adopting an ecological perspective to identify motivation sources and underlying regulatory mechanisms. Based on this review, Zhang argues for the reconceptualization of research on physical education teacher motivation and proposes

an alternative theoretical framework that integrates external-regulation motivation with the job demand–job resource model, which offers a conceptual lens for future studies that link motivation to the job environment.

Kasimoglu (2021) also highlighted that various psychosocial factors are linked to significant issues of adjustment and low motivation among a considerable number of teachers. The motivation of physical education teachers plays a crucial role in their interactions with students and in achieving effective lesson outcomes. This study aimed to assess the motivation levels of physical education teachers in relation to several variables. Using a descriptive survey model, the study compared physical education teachers based on gender, age, marital status, and school type. The sample included 206 physical education teachers working in secondary schools and high schools in the provinces of Aksaray, Karaman, and Konya, Turkey. Data were collected using intrinsic and extrinsic motivation scales. The study found that the extrinsic motivation levels of the teachers were relatively low, with teachers in private schools exhibiting particularly low levels of both extrinsic and general motivation. The findings also revealed that motivation levels varied according to gender, age, marital status, and school type.

Mäkelä et al. (2014) conducted a study examining Finnish physical education (PE) teachers' intentions to leave the profession and the factors influencing these decisions. Method: A large sample of PE teachers ($N = 808$), who graduated between 1980 and 2008 (432 women, 376 men), participated by responding to a modified job satisfaction and teacher follow-up questionnaire. The questionnaire gathered information on career perceptions, intentions, and current job duties. Results indicated that among the respondents, 26% were considering leaving the PE teaching profession, while an additional 13% were transitioning to other teaching roles but planned to remain within the education system. To identify the reasons for considering departure, principal axis factoring with direct oblimin rotation was applied to 35 questionnaire items, which were categorized into factors such as the status of the PE profession, pupils, working conditions, colleagues, expertise, workload, administration, and stress. The most significant reasons for considering leaving included inadequate facilities, poor equipment, and isolation from peers. Additional factors involved working conditions, low status of PE teachers, and workload. Women reported that workload and stress were more significant factors in their decision to leave than men ($p = .010-.040$, $d = 0.34-0.43$). Teachers aged 40 to 44 years were the largest group contemplating leaving the profession. The study conclude that thirty-nine percent of PE teachers were considering leaving the profession. Despite facing various challenges, the majority of PE teachers planned to continue in the teaching field. Improved resources and greater collegial support may help reduce the intention to leave the profession.

Uğraş and Özen (2019) identified two key themes that influence teaching motivation: intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors included a sense of responsibility, conscience, love for teaching, achieving success, being useful, and deserving the salary earned. On the other hand, extrinsic factors were related to students' interest in the subject, parents' attitudes, school administration's approach, availability of facilities and equipment, public perception of physical education, and the influence of colleagues. The study found that physical education teachers' motivations were generally low, with intrinsic motivation levels being moderate. The intrinsic motivators identified were a sense of responsibility, conscience, a passion for teaching, success, contributing to others, and receiving fair compensation.

Relationship Between Attitudes Toward Physical Activity and Career Motivation for Teaching Physical Education of the Physical Education

Al-Rawahi and Al-Yarabi (2013) aimed to explore the connection between physical education teachers' attitudes toward engaging in physical activity and their motivations for selecting physical education as a teaching career. Data was collected using two questionnaires from a sample of 98 participants. The results indicated that the participants held positive attitudes toward physical activity. Additionally, they identified both intrinsic and extrinsic reasons for choosing physical education as their profession. The findings also highlighted a significant correlation between the participants' attitudes toward physical activity and their motivations for pursuing a career in physical education.

Synthesis of the Review

The synthesis of the reviewed literature presents a comprehensive understanding of the interrelated constructs of job satisfaction, attitudes toward physical activity, and career motivation among physical education (PE) teachers. These themes provide critical insight into the factors that influence PE teachers' professional lives, career persistence, and teaching effectiveness.

Regarding attitudes toward physical activity, a consistent pattern of positive perception emerges among PE teachers. Research underscores the importance of aligning physical education programs with the interests and contexts of both students and teachers (Gumanoy et al., 2022). Teachers recognize the value of fitness assessments and physical activities, with factors such as gender and age influencing their engagement and enjoyment (Marques et al., 2022). Additionally, burnout, particularly depersonalization, has been found to negatively affect teachers' physical activity attitudes, which point to the need for interventions that promote teacher well-being (Relacion, 2023).

The job satisfaction of PE teachers is largely shaped by both organizational and personal factors. Key determinants such as administrative support, work-life balance, financial incentives, and resource availability strongly influence overall satisfaction (Gazali et al., 2024; Hao et al., 2018). Findings from multiple studies reveal that satisfaction levels vary by gender, years of experience, and professional rank, with younger teachers favoring leadership support and senior teachers placing value on salary and welfare. Employment, beyond its economic role, also fulfills social and psychological needs, which are aligned with the perspectives of Çakır (2001) on the various roles of work in human life.

Career motivation among PE teachers is deeply influenced by both intrinsic factors (e.g., love for teaching, sense of responsibility, personal fulfillment) and extrinsic elements (e.g., job conditions, administrative support, public perception) (Uğraş & Özen, 2019; Kasimoglu, 2021). Studies reveal motivation disparities depending on gender, age, and school type, with private school teachers reporting lower motivation. Job-related stressors such as inadequate resources, isolation, and heavy workloads significantly impact the intent to stay in the profession, especially among mid-career teachers (Mäkelä et al., 2014). Zhang (2021) calls for a reconceptualized theoretical approach that integrates motivational theory with the job demand–resource model to better understand these dynamics.

Lastly, there is a clear positive relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation in teaching PE. Teachers who value and enjoy physical activity are more likely to be intrinsically and extrinsically motivated in their careers (Kiran, 2017; Al-Rawahi & Al-Yarabi, 2013). This correlation suggests that fostering a positive culture of physical activity among educators could enhance their commitment and performance.

To summarize, the synthesis highlights that job satisfaction, attitudes toward physical activity, and career motivation are intricately connected in shaping the professional identity and efficacy of physical education teachers. Addressing these areas holistically through institutional support, professional development, and policy reforms can lead to improved teacher retention, satisfaction, and student outcomes in physical education.

Theoretical Framework

The following models and theories can guide the research:

Self-Determination Theory (SDT). This theory, proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985), posits that individuals are most motivated when their basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are met. In the context of this study, the attitudes of PE instructors toward physical activity may reflect their intrinsic motivation for teaching, while their job satisfaction could influence how these basic needs are fulfilled. SDT can help explain how job satisfaction moderates the relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation by assessing how satisfied instructors feel with their autonomy, competence, and relationships within their work environment.

Job Satisfaction Theory. Job satisfaction is a critical factor in employee motivation and performance. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959) suggests that job satisfaction is influenced by both hygiene factors (e.g., pay, working conditions) and motivators (e.g., achievement, recognition). This theory could provide insight into how job satisfaction, as a moderating factor, might influence PE instructors' career motivation and their attitudes toward physical activity. If the hygiene factors and motivators in the job environment at the higher education institutions are favorable, job satisfaction may enhance the positive relationship between instructors' attitudes toward physical activity and their motivation to teach.

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). Bandura's (1986) SCT emphasizes the role of cognitive, behavioral, and environmental factors in shaping individuals' actions and motivation. This theory can be used to explain how PE instructors' attitudes and motivation toward teaching are shaped by their self-efficacy beliefs (confidence in their ability to succeed in their role) and the social support they receive (colleagues, students, and administration). In the case of job satisfaction, SCT can help identify how positive or negative workplace experiences impact instructors' self-efficacy and career motivation.

Expectancy Theory. Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964) proposes that individuals are motivated to act based on their expectations that their efforts will lead to desired outcomes. For PE instructors, job satisfaction may shape their expectations about the rewards (both intrinsic and extrinsic) of teaching. This theory can explain how the satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their work environment influences their motivation to teach and their attitudes toward physical activity.

Conceptual Framework

In this study, attitudes toward physical activity directly influence career motivation for teaching physical education. Moreover, the job satisfaction of the instructors moderates this relationship. Job satisfaction could either strengthen or weaken the impact of attitudes toward physical activity on career motivation. This framework provides a structured way to understand how different factors (attitudes, motivation, and job satisfaction) interact and affect PE instructors' professional motivation.

The framework could be illustrated by the figure below:

Derived from the theoretical framework with additional variables

Direct Relationships

Attitudes Toward Physical Activity → Career Motivation

Positive attitudes toward physical activity are likely to lead to higher career motivation in PE instructors, as instructors who value physical activity may be more motivated to teach it to students and excel in their profession.

Moderated Relationship

Job satisfaction → moderates the relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation:

Moderation Effect. Job satisfaction can influence the strength or direction of the relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation. For example:

High Job Satisfaction. Instructors with high job satisfaction may experience a stronger, more positive relationship between their attitudes toward physical activity and their career motivation. They are likely to feel more engaged and committed to their teaching role.

Low Job Satisfaction. Instructors with low job satisfaction may have a weaker or more negative relationship between their attitudes and career motivation. Despite having positive attitudes toward physical activity, low job satisfaction may decrease their motivation to continue in the profession.

Statement of the Problem

1. To what extent is the attitude toward physical activity among the PE teachers?
2. To what extent is the career motivation for teaching PE among PE teachers?
3. To what extent is the effect of the attitude toward physical activity in career motivation?
4. To what extent do job satisfaction moderate attitude toward physical activity and career motivation?
5. Based on the findings (Job Satisfaction Towards Attitudes and Career Motivation of the Physical Education Instructors in Selected Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro), what recommendations could be made?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: Attitude toward physical activity among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

H₀₂: Career motivation for teaching PE among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

H₀₃: Attitude toward physical activity has no significant effect on the career motivation of the physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

H₀₄: Job satisfaction does not significantly moderate attitude towards physical activity and career motivation of Physical Education instructors at the selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

Significance of the Study

The study will provide insights into the significance of job satisfaction in shaping PE instructors' motivation and attitudes toward teaching. The findings could guide strategies to enhance instructors' job satisfaction, which could improve their teaching effectiveness and student outcomes in PE programs. This study could also provide a detailed action plan for PE instructors as to how their teaching could be more effective.

Scope and Limitation

This study was conducted among the three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro, namely Occidental Mindoro State College (OMSC), Philippine Central Island College (PCIC), and Divine Word College of San Jose (DWCSJ), which focus specifically on the regular physical education instructors within these institutions. The participants consist of six (6) instructors of OMSC, two (2) from PCIC, and one (1) from DWCSJ, from various teaching levels, such as junior and senior high school, as well as the college level. The study was limited to these instructors who are employed at the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro during the academic year 2024-2025, which could provide a background of their current attitudes toward physical activity, career motivation, and job satisfaction. The key variables in this study include attitudes toward physical activity, career motivation, and job satisfaction, with job satisfaction serving as the moderating variable. Attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation was assessed using researcher-made questionnaire, while job satisfaction was measured based on instructors' satisfaction with their work environment and resources.

The research design for this study is descriptive-predictive, which helped establish the relationships between these variables and explore the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the attitude toward physical

activity and career motivation. Data was gathered online through Google form link which was sent and administered to the physical education instructors at the three said schools.

One significant limitation of this study is the sample size, as it focused solely on the nine (9) physical education instructors at the three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro. This limits the generalizability of the findings to other institutions or regions, particularly in settings where the context may differ from that of these institutions. Additionally, the study used a cross-sectional design, meaning the data reflected the instructors' attitudes, job satisfaction, and career motivation at a single point in time. This design did not allow for the examination of how these factors evolve over time or as a result of interventions.

The study relied on self-reported data, which can introduce biases, such as social desirability bias, where respondents provided answers that they perceive to be socially acceptable or favorable. This could impact the accuracy and validity of the reported results. Furthermore, the study may not be able to fully control for other potential confounding variables, such as external factors like personal circumstances, government policies, or economic conditions, which could influence the attitudes and motivation of PE instructors.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-predictive research design to investigate the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation for teaching physical education among the physical education instructors at the higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro. The descriptive aspect of the study allowed for the systematic collection and analysis of data related to the instructors' attitudes toward physical activity, career motivation, and job satisfaction. One-sample test was used to determine the extent of attitude toward physical activity and career motivation. Pearson product moment correlation was used to determine the extent to which attitude toward physical activity affects the career motivation, while multiple regression analysis helped identify whether job satisfaction moderates the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation.

Population, Samples, and Sampling Technique

Population

The population for this study consisted of physical education instructors employed at the three (3) higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro during the Academic Year 2024-2025. This population is composed of individuals who are actively teaching physical education courses and who, therefore, possess relevant experience and insight into the attitudes, job satisfaction, and career motivations explored in this study. The population included instructors from both secondary and higher education levels to ensure that a diverse range of instructors with varying levels of teaching experience and professional backgrounds are represented.

Sample

Due to the small number of regular PE instructors cumulatively across the three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro, all determined regular PE instructors were considered in the sample.

Inclusion criteria for the sample:

- Physical education instructors currently employed as a regular faculty at the three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro during the 2024-2025 academic year.
- Instructors who are teaching physical education courses at the three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.
- Instructors who consent to participate in the study after receiving a clear explanation of the research objectives and the ethical guidelines for participation.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a purposive sampling technique, particularly complete enumeration due to a limited number of regular PE instructors, which is appropriate for selecting participants who have specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. Purposive sampling ensured that only those physical education instructors who are actively involved in teaching physical education and who are able to provide valuable insights into the study variables (attitudes toward physical activity, job satisfaction, and career motivation) are selected.

Sample Size

The sample size of nine (9) PE instructors was determined based on the total number of physical education instructors at three higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro. Since the number of instructors is relatively small (e.g., fewer than 30), a census approach was used, where all eligible instructors were invited to participate in the study to achieve statistically significant results.

Exclusion Criteria

Instructors who do not meet the inclusion criteria, such as those who are not actively teaching physical education or who do not provide consent to participate, were excluded from the study. Additionally, part-time instructors who may not have enough interaction or direct involvement in the teaching process were excluded if they do not meet the criteria specified for full-time instructors.

The Research Instruments

To investigate the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation for teaching physical education among instructors at the three higher education

institutions in Occidental Mindoro, a researcher-made set of questionnaires was used to collect the relevant data.

Attitudes Toward Physical Activity Scale. This was employed to measure the physical education instructors' attitudes toward physical activity. This scale assessed their general beliefs, feelings, and intentions related to physical activity, and how these attitudes might influence their teaching and motivation in the classroom. This scale will be interpreted using the following scores range:

1.0 – 1.49	=	Very Negative
1.50 – 2.49	=	Negative
2.50 – 3.49	=	Neutral
3.50 – 4.49	=	Positive
4.50 – 5.00	=	Very Positive

Job Satisfaction Survey. This was used to measure the physical education instructors' level of job satisfaction. This survey assessed various factors that contribute to an instructor's overall job satisfaction, such as leadership support and working environment. Job satisfaction is expected to play a moderating role in how instructors' attitudes toward physical activity influence their motivation to teach physical education.

1.0 – 1.49	=	Very Dissatisfied
1.50 – 2.49	=	Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	=	Moderately Satisfied
3.50 – 4.49	=	Satisfied
4.50 – 5.00	=	Very Satisfied

Career Motivation for Teaching Physical Education Scale. This was developed to specifically measure the motivations of physical education instructors in choosing teaching as their career. This scale assessed both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, such as passion for teaching, the desire to contribute to students' health, job security, and salary.

1.0 – 1.49	=	Very Low
1.50 – 2.49	=	Low
2.50 – 3.49	=	Moderate
3.50 – 4.49	=	High
4.50 – 5.00	=	Very High

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments, the researcher conducted a pilot test of the questionnaires with a small group of ten (10) physical education teachers working in the Department of

Education (DepEd) schools, who are typically not included in the main study sample. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated for each scale to assess internal consistency and ensure that the instruments are reliable for data collection.

Validity Test

To ensure that the research instruments effectively measure the intended variables which are attitudes toward physical activity, job satisfaction, and career motivation, a content validity process was conducted. The initial draft of the instruments was reviewed by a panel of experts consisting of professionals in physical education, educational psychology, and research methodology. These experts evaluated the appropriateness, clarity, and alignment of each item with the research objectives. Their feedback were used to refine the wording, structure, and content of the questionnaires to eliminate ambiguity and enhance their accuracy. Furthermore, face validity was checked through a pilot testing phase with a small group of instructors who are not part of the main study. Their responses and comments provided insight into whether the questions are understood as intended, which could lead to further refinement if needed.

Reliability Test

The reliability of the instruments was established through internal consistency measures. A pilot test was conducted with a small group of ten (10) physical education teachers from Department of Education who are not included in the final sample. The collected data was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient to determine the internal consistency of each scale. The reliability statistics of the four scales used in the study indicate acceptable to high internal consistency. The Leadership Support scale, with a Cronbach's alpha of .842, demonstrates high reliability, which suggests that the five items effectively measure this construct under job satisfaction. The Working Environment scale also shows acceptable reliability with an alpha of .734, which indicates that the items are consistently capturing aspects of the workplace setting. Similarly, the Attitude Towards Physical Activity scale has a reliability coefficient of .771, while the Career Motivation for Teaching Physical Education scale has an alpha of .785, both indicating satisfactory internal consistency for evaluating respondents' perspectives and motivations.

Rubric (Rating Scale)

Each of the three variables were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale to capture respondents' perceptions, feelings, and motivations with respect to each variable. The Attitudes Toward Physical Activity Scale, Job Satisfaction Survey, and Career Motivation Scale used a scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The use of a Likert scale facilitated quantifiable data collection and allowed for meaningful statistical analyses by capturing the degree of agreement or intensity of the respondents' feelings toward each item.

Ethical Considerations

The study adheres to the ethical standards of educational research and institutional guidelines. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. The purpose of the study, the procedures involved, the confidentiality of responses, and the right to withdraw at any time was clearly communicated to all participants. No personally identifiable information was collected, and data were treated with strict confidentiality. The researcher ensured that all data are stored securely and used solely for academic purposes.

Statistical Tests

The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize the participants' responses and provided a general overview of their attitudes, levels of job satisfaction, and career motivations. For inferential analysis, one-sample t-test was used to determine the extent of attitude toward physical activity and career motivation. Pearson product moment correlation was used to determine the extent to which attitude toward physical activity effects the career motivation. To test whether job satisfaction moderates the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation, a moderation analysis was performed using multiple regression. Specifically, the interaction term between attitudes and job satisfaction was examined to assess its significance. A significance level of 0.05 was used in all statistical tests to determine the acceptance or rejection of null hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.

Extent of the attitude toward physical activity of the Physical Education Teachers in selected Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	t	Sig. (2-tailed test)	Significance
1	I believe regular physical activity is essential for a healthy lifestyle.	5.000 (To a Very High Extent)	.0000				
2	I enjoy participating in physical activities during my free time.	4.667 (To a Very High Extent)	.5000	4.6667	28.000	.000	Significant
3	I feel confident promoting physical activity to my students.	4.889 (To a Very High Extent)	.3333	4.8889	44.000	.000	Significant

4	I stay physically active because it improves my mental health and physical well-being.	4.778 (To a Very High Extent)	.4410	4.7778	32.505	.000	Significant
5	I consider physical activity as an important part of being an effective PE instructor.	5.000 (To a Very High Extent)	.0000				
		N = 9	df = 8	$\alpha = .05$	test value = 0		

H₀₁: Attitude toward physical activity among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that the extent to which Physical Education teachers demonstrate positive attitudes toward physical activity is statistically significant. Mean scores for all five indicators range from 4.667 to 5.000, which shows that their attitudes are consistently rated to a very high extent. This indicates that teachers not only value physical activity but also view it as essential to both their personal well-being and their professional role as educators. With standard deviations ranging from .0000 to .5000, the responses show strong consistency and close agreement among participants.

All indicators that underwent testing yielded p-values of .000, which confirms that the means significantly exceed the test value of 3.5. The positive t-values, supported by strong mean differences (4.6667 to 4.8889), highlight the teachers' strong commitment to maintaining an active lifestyle, promoting physical activity to students, and recognizing its importance to teaching effectiveness. These results strongly reject the null hypothesis, which suggested that the attitudes toward physical activity were not significant.

The findings clearly demonstrate that Physical Education teachers uphold very high regard for physical activity as part of their identity and practice. They view it as integral not only for maintaining health but also for fulfilling their professional responsibilities. The consistency of these results affirms that their outlook toward physical activity is both personal and professional, which underscores its role in fostering holistic well-being and effective teaching.

Table 2.

Extent of the Career Motivation in Teaching PE of the Physical Education Teachers in Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	t	Sig. (2-tailed test)	Significance
1	I feel motivated to continue growing in my teaching career.	4.889 (To a Very High Extent)	.0000				
2	I see myself working as a physical education instructor in the long term.	4.667 (To a Very High Extent)	.5000	4.6667	28.000	.000	Significant
3	I actively seek ways to improve my skills and teaching effectiveness.	4.778 (To a Very High Extent)	.3333	4.8889	44.000	.000	Significant
4	I am passionate about making a positive impact on my students' lives through teaching.	4.889 (To a Very High Extent)	.4410	4.7778	32.505	.000	Significant
5	I am committed to advancing my career in the field of education.	4.778 (To a Very High Extent)	.0000				

N = 9

df = 8

 $\alpha = .05$

test value = 0

H₀₂: Career motivation for teaching PE among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

The results presented in Table 2 reveal that the extent of career motivation in teaching Physical Education among teachers in Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro is statistically significant. Mean scores for the five indicators range from 4.667 to 4.889, which reflects that teachers demonstrate their career motivation to a very high extent. This suggests a consistent drive to pursue growth, long-term commitment, and passion for their role as Physical Education instructors. With standard deviations ranging from .0000 to .5000, the results show strong agreement among respondents.

Indicators that underwent testing yielded p-values of .000, which confirms that the means significantly exceed the test value of 3.5. The positive t-values, supported by strong mean differences (4.6667 to 4.8889), highlight the respondents' commitment to professional growth, dedication to their teaching career, and determination to contribute positively to their students' lives. These results strongly reject the null hypothesis, which suggested that career motivation in teaching PE was not significant.

The findings clearly demonstrate that Physical Education teachers possess very high levels of motivation to continue developing their careers in education. Their strong sense of purpose, passion for teaching, and long-term vision underscore the value they place on their profession, showing alignment between their personal aspirations and their professional responsibilities.

Table 3.

Extent of Effects of Attitude Towards Physical Activity towards Career Motivation in Teaching PE of the Physical Education Teachers in Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
Attitude towards Physical Activities	.775 ^a	.600	.543	.2342

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attitude towards Physical Activities

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.576	1	.576	10.500	.014 ^b
	Residual	.384	7	.055		
	Total	.960	8			

a. Dependent Variable: Career Motivation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Attitude towards Physical Activities

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.040	1.804		-.577	.582
	Attitude towards Physical Activities	1.200	.370	.775	3.240	.014

a. Dependent Variable: Career Motivation

H₀₃: Attitude toward physical activity has no significant effect on the career motivation of the physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

The results presented in Table 3 reveal that the extent of the effects of attitude toward physical activity on career motivation in teaching Physical Education among teachers in Higher Education Institutions in Occidental Mindoro is statistically significant. The model summary shows a correlation coefficient of $R = .775$, which indicates a strong positive relationship between the two variables. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .600$) suggests that 60% of the variance in career motivation can be explained by attitude toward physical activity, while the adjusted R^2 of .543 confirms the model's reliability. The standard error of estimate (.2342) reflects the close fit of the data to the regression line.

The ANOVA results further support the model's significance, with an F-value of 10.500 and a corresponding p-value of .014, which is less than .05. This finding confirms that attitude toward physical activity significantly predicts career motivation in teaching PE.

The coefficients table provides further evidence of this relationship. The unstandardized coefficient for attitude toward physical activities ($B = 1.200$, $SE = .370$) shows that for every one-unit increase in attitude toward physical activity, career motivation increases by 1.200 units. The standardized beta coefficient of .775 indicates a strong effect size, while the t-value of 3.240 with a significance level of .014 reinforces that this predictor is statistically significant. On the other hand, the constant value (-1.040) was not significant ($p = .582$), indicating that the intercept alone does not contribute meaningfully to the model.

Overall, these results confirm that attitude toward physical activity exerts a significant and positive influence on the career motivation of Physical Education teachers, demonstrating a substantial link between personal outlook on physical activity and professional drive in teaching.

Table 4.

Moderating role of job satisfaction in the attitude towards physical activity and career motivation of the physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Attitude towards Physical Activities	Between Groups	.113	4	.028	.395	.805
	Within Groups	.287	4	.072		
	Total	.400	8			
Career Motivation	Between Groups	.613	4	.153	1.769	.297
	Within Groups	.347	4	.087		
	Total	.960	8			

H₀₄: Job satisfaction does not significantly moderate attitude towards physical activity and career motivation of Physical Education instructors at the selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

Table 4 presents the ANOVA results for the moderating role of job satisfaction in the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

For the variable attitude toward physical activities, the ANOVA yielded an F-value of 0.395 with a p-value of 0.805. Since the p-value is far above the conventional 0.05 significance level, there is no significant difference in attitude toward physical activity across different levels of job satisfaction. This means that, regardless of how satisfied the teachers are with their jobs, their attitudes toward physical activity remain relatively the same.

Similarly, for career motivation, the F-value is 1.769 with a p-value of 0.297. Again, this is not statistically significant, showing that career motivation does not differ significantly among teachers grouped by their level of job satisfaction. Thus, even when job satisfaction varies, the level of career motivation among the teachers remains consistently high.

The implication to its beneficiaries, particularly school administrators, HR units, and program developers, is that while job satisfaction is important for general teacher well-being, it does not play a moderating role in shaping PE instructors' personal attitudes toward physical activity or their motivation to stay in the profession. This suggests that their passion for physical activity and teaching may be driven more by intrinsic or professional values rather than job-related satisfaction alone. As a result, interventions to boost career motivation may benefit more from focusing on internal drivers and professional development rather than purely improving job satisfaction metrics.

Conclusion

The study could lead to the development of an action plan for more effective teaching of Physical Education in higher education institutions after determining the interplay of job satisfaction on the attitude toward physical activity and career motivation of the Physical Education instructors.

Specifically, the study addressed the following salient areas of concern:

1. To what extent is the attitude toward physical activity among the PE teachers?
2. To what extent is the career motivation for teaching PE among PE teachers?
3. To what extent is the effect of the attitude toward physical activity in career motivation?
4. To what extent do job satisfaction moderate attitude toward physical activity and career motivation?

The conclusions are derived from the results of the hypothesis testing.

H₀₁: Attitude toward physical activity among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

The test result was to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that attitudes among physical education teachers in higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is significant.

This outcome is consistent with prior research that has highlighted the central role of teachers' perspectives on physical activity in shaping their professional engagement and motivation. For instance, Gumanoy et al. (2022) found that Madrasah teachers in Marawi City held positive attitudes toward physical activity and supported the integration of physical education in the curriculum. Similarly, Marques et al.

(2022) observed that Portuguese PE teachers displayed slightly positive attitudes toward fitness tests, with variations across gender and age, further affirming that attitudes toward physical activity influence how teachers perceive and carry out their professional roles. In another study, Kiran (2017) showed that teachers with favorable attitudes toward physical exercise were motivated to pursue teaching careers in PE, indicating a direct link between their outlook on physical activity and career decisions. Relacion (2023) also underscored that while burnout levels were low, teachers maintained high attitudes toward physical activity, with depersonalization emerging as a significant factor influencing those attitudes.

Taken together, these studies reinforce the findings of the present research: teachers' attitudes toward physical activity are not only statistically significant but also meaningful in the context of their career motivation and teaching performance. The alignment of these results with existing literature strengthens the conclusion that attitudes toward physical activity form a crucial determinant in shaping professional identity and sustaining motivation in the field of physical education.

H₀₂: Career motivation for teaching PE among physical education teachers in selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is not significant.

The test result was to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that career motivation for teaching PE among physical education teachers in selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro is significant.

This outcome demonstrates that teachers in the field show high levels of professional drive, which is strongly linked to their positive attitudes toward physical activity and their satisfaction with their roles. Studies support this finding by showing how attitudes toward physical activity influence professional outlooks. For example, Gumanoy et al. (2022) revealed that Madrasah teachers in Marawi City exhibited favorable attitudes toward physical activity, with high acceptance of its integration into their curriculum. Marques et al. (2022) also found that Portuguese PE teachers expressed positive perspectives on the role of fitness tests in fostering student health, with attitudes influenced by gender and age. Similarly, Kiran (2017) and Relacion (2023) highlighted that teachers' positive perceptions of physical activity contribute not only to their well-being but also to their professional motivation, with burnout, particularly depersonalization, showing negative impacts on these attitudes.

Job satisfaction also plays a crucial role in strengthening career motivation among PE teachers. Gazali et al. (2024) emphasized that administrative support, work-life balance, and financial incentives are central factors in shaping teacher satisfaction. Hao et al. (2018) confirmed that working conditions and interpersonal relationships contribute strongly to job satisfaction levels, though differences emerge across gender and years of experience. Employment itself serves broader psychological and social purposes, providing teachers with a sense of meaning and accomplishment (Çakır, 2001, as cited in Yuceloglu Keskin & Bayram, 2020). When these needs are met, teachers are more motivated to persist in their careers and remain effective in their roles.

Research on career motivation specifically shows that intrinsic and extrinsic factors intersect to sustain teachers' commitment to PE. Uğraş and Özen (2019) reported that intrinsic drivers, such as responsibility and passion for teaching, work alongside extrinsic factors, including administrative support and availability of resources. Kasimoglu (2021) observed that variations in motivation levels depend on personal and institutional contexts, while Mäkelä et al. (2014) cautioned that inadequate facilities, low status, and heavy workloads are reasons some PE teachers consider leaving the profession. Nevertheless, Zhang (2021) argued for a broader theoretical framework that situates motivation within job demands and resources, reinforcing its complexity and importance.

Finally, the link between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation has been consistently established. Al-Rawahi and Al-Yarabi (2013) found a significant correlation between positive attitudes toward physical activity and the motivation to pursue PE teaching as a career. Kiran (2017) confirmed similar findings, suggesting that those who value physical activity are more likely to sustain high levels of professional commitment. In this context, the rejection of the null hypothesis in the present study aligns with existing literature, showing that career motivation in teaching PE is not only significant but also shaped by attitudes, satisfaction, and contextual support systems.

H₀₃: Attitude toward physical activity has no significant effect on the career motivation of the physical education teachers in selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

The test result was to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that attitude toward physical activity has significant effect on the career motivation of the physical education teachers in selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

This finding is consistent with earlier studies. For instance, Gumanoy et al. (2022) found that Madrasah teachers in Marawi City exhibited positive attitudes toward physical activity, which reinforced the acceptability of including it in their curriculum. Similarly, Marques et al. (2022) reported that Portuguese PE teachers maintained slightly positive attitudes toward fitness testing, which shaped their engagement and practices in school settings. Both studies indicate that attitudes influence teachers' willingness to integrate and promote physical activities within their professional roles. Relacion (2023) further emphasized that teachers with higher levels of positive attitudes toward physical activity reported lower burnout, establishing a link between attitude and professional well-being.

In addition, Kiran (2017) demonstrated that teachers' positive attitudes toward physical activities were correlated with their motivations for entering and continuing in the profession of teaching physical education. Likewise, Al-Rawahi and Al-Yarabi (2013) confirmed a significant connection between teachers' positive views of physical activity and their motivations for choosing and sustaining a career in PE. These findings align with the present study, which shows that attitude toward physical activity directly contributes to career motivation.

The role of motivation in teaching PE is also reinforced by studies on job satisfaction. Gazali et al. (2024) and Hao et al. (2018) showed that workplace support, working conditions, and resources play key roles in shaping teacher satisfaction, which, in turn, influence their motivation and persistence in the profession. In the same way, Kasimoglu (2021) and Uğraş and Özen (2019) identified intrinsic and extrinsic factors, such as responsibility, passion for teaching, administrative support, and public perception, that either strengthen or weaken PE teachers' motivation. These findings mirror the present results by showing that positive psychological dispositions, like attitudes toward physical activity, have a significant effect on motivation to remain in the teaching profession.

Overall, the present study contributes to the growing evidence that attitudes toward physical activity are not only a matter of personal preference but also a critical factor influencing professional motivation. Consistent with previous research, the results highlight the strong link between how teachers perceive physical activity and their career commitment, confirming that positive attitudes foster higher levels of career motivation in teaching Physical Education (Kiran, 2017; Al-Rawahi & Al-Yarabi, 2013).

H₀₄: Job satisfaction does not significantly moderate attitude towards physical activity and career motivation of Physical Education instructors at the selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

The test result was to accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis that job satisfaction does not significantly moderate attitude towards physical activity and career motivation of Physical Education instructors at the selected higher education institutions in Occidental Mindoro.

These findings align with existing literature. For instance, Gumanoy et al. (2022) observed that teachers generally demonstrate positive attitudes toward physical activity, which translates into higher acceptance of physical education within the school curriculum. Similarly, Marques et al. (2022) highlighted that teachers' perceptions of fitness and activity programs shape how they value and integrate physical activity in their practice. This suggests that positive attitudes among teachers are not only linked to professional competence but also to sustained career engagement.

Research also supports the connection between physical activity attitudes and motivation. Kiran (2017) and Al-Rawahi and Al-Yarabi (2013) both found that teachers who hold favorable attitudes toward physical activity tend to exhibit stronger intrinsic and extrinsic motivations for pursuing a career in physical education. Likewise, Relacion (2023) emphasized that while burnout may negatively influence attitudes, teachers with high regard for physical activity maintain better resilience and motivation in their profession.

Career motivation cannot be separated from broader workplace factors such as job satisfaction. Studies by Gazali et al. (2024) and Hao et al. (2018) noted that working conditions, leadership support, and financial incentives shape teachers' overall satisfaction, which in turn sustains career motivation. At the same time, intrinsic and extrinsic motivators such as personal fulfillment, responsibility, and recognition also play crucial roles in maintaining motivation (Uğraş & Özen, 2019; Kasimoglu, 2021). The interplay between these factors indicates that attitudes toward physical activity are not isolated, but are embedded within a broader professional context that influences career persistence and development.

In summary, the rejection of the null hypothesis is consistent with the body of literature that points to a strong and significant relationship between attitudes toward physical activity and career motivation among Physical Education teachers. Positive attitudes foster greater professional commitment, enhance job satisfaction, and encourage long-term engagement in teaching (Mäkelä et al., 2014; Zhang, 2021). This demonstrates that nurturing favorable attitudes toward physical activity is integral to sustaining and motivating teachers in their professional journey.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are strongly recommended:

1. On the regression results:

it is recommended that higher education institutions strengthen initiatives that foster positive attitudes of Physical Education teachers toward physical activity. Since the regression analysis showed that attitude toward physical activity significantly predicts career motivation, with 60% of the variance in motivation explained by this factor, institutions should consider embedding structured wellness and fitness programs that actively engage teachers. Providing professional development opportunities focused on both physical activity promotion and personal well-being can also sustain motivation levels.

Additionally, policies that recognize and reward teachers who actively model healthy and active lifestyles may encourage greater alignment between personal attitudes and professional commitment.

2. On the ANOVA results:

In terms of the ANOVA results, which revealed a statistically significant relationship between attitude toward physical activity and career motivation, it is recommended that administrators design interventions that target specific groups of teachers based on their varying needs and circumstances. For example, workshops and mentorship programs could be tailored to enhance motivation across different career stages, while institutional support could be strengthened to minimize potential barriers such as workload, lack of facilities, or limited recognition. Since the variance explained was significant, but not absolute, supplementary factors such as job satisfaction, administrative support, and working conditions should also be integrated into broader institutional strategies. This combined focus would ensure that while positive attitudes are nurtured, other contextual elements that influence career motivation are equally addressed.

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